

USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN MOTHER TONGUE AND READING LITERACY CLASSES

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ANNOTATION: This article presents interactive methods that can be used in mother tongue and reading literacy classes for elementary school students. In addition, some examples of interactive methods that can be used in the teaching process are given. The order of their application and their practical importance in the field are also discussed.

KEY WORDS: skill, pedagogy, education, opinion, competence, skill, experience, activity, methodology, method, recommendation, conclusion, practice, opinion.

Currently, modern teaching methods are widely used in the educational process. The use of modern teaching methods leads to high efficiency in the teaching process. It is appropriate to choose these methods based on the didactic task of each lesson. While preserving the traditional form of the lesson, enriching it with various methods that activate the activity of the learners, will lead to an increase in the level of mastery of the learners.

Today, in a number of developed countries, the methods that form the basis of great experience in the application of modern pedagogical technologies guaranteeing the effectiveness of the educational process are being used under the name of interactive methods. Interactive educational methods are currently the most common and widely used methods in all types of educational institutions. At the same time, there are many types of interactive educational methods, suitable for the purposes of implementing almost all tasks of the educational process. In practice, it is possible to select the ones suitable for specific purposes and use them accordingly. This situation has created the problem of choosing the right interactive educational methods for the realization of certain goals.

For this purpose, the lesson process should be organized rationally, the teacher should increase the interest of the learners and encourage their activity in the educational process, divide the educational material into small parts and open their contents intellectually. It is necessary to use methods such as attack, work in small groups, debate, problem situation, reference text, project, role-playing, and encourage learners to do practical exercises independently.

An interactive method is to solve an activity or a problem in a mutual dialogue, in the course of thinking in a mutual debate, with unity. The advantage of this method is that the whole activity teaches the student to think independently and prepares him for an independent life.

When choosing interactive methods of teaching, the purpose of education, the number and capabilities of students, the educational and material conditions of the educational institution, the duration of education, the pedagogical skills of the teacher, etc. are taken into account.

Interactive methods mean methods that activate learners and encourage them to think independently, with the learner at the center of the educational process. When these methods

are used, the teacher invites the learner to actively participate. The learner is involved throughout the process.

The benefits of a learner-centered approach include:

- o study-learning with a higher educational effect;
- o high motivation of the learner;
- o consideration of previously acquired knowledge;
- o adaptation of the educational process to the goals and needs of the learner;
- o support of the learner's initiative and responsibility;
- o learning by doing;
- o creation of conditions for two-way feedback.

Thus, the use of interactive methods in the process of teaching subjects has its own characteristics. Thorough study and practical application of each interactive method used in educational practice expands the thinking of students and has a positive effect on finding the right solution to the problem. Increases creativity and activity of students. When various theoretical and practical problems are analyzed through interactive methods, the expansion and deepening of the knowledge, skills, and abilities of students is achieved.

It is clear from the above that it is necessary to properly analyze the interactive education methods and classify them on this basis. Below we present general comments on this issue.

When classifying these methods, they can be divided into interactive methods, interactive educational strategies, and interactive graphic organizers.

Currently, the most popular interactive educational methods are:

1. Interactive methods: "Case-study" (or "Educational cases"), "Blister survey", "Modeling", "Creative work", "Problematic education", etc.

2. Interactive educational strategies. When distinguishing interactive educational strategies from the composition of interactive educational methods, the approach to organizing group work is based on the fact that, in a certain sense, it is compared to strategic planning. In fact, these strategies are more related to interactive educational methods, and there are no other differences between them.

3. Interactive graphic organizers: "Fish skeleton", "BBB", "Conceptual table", "Venn diagram", "T-table", "Insert", "Cluster", "Why?", "How?" and b. The separation of interactive graphic organizers is based on the fact that the main ideas are expressed in written form in various graphic forms. In fact, working with these graphic organizers is more related to interactive educational methods, and there are no other differences between them.

Interactive educational methods are often used simultaneously with various forms of training technologies. The use of these methods increases the activity of the training participants and improves the effectiveness of education.

In this regard, according to the above classification, the ease of use of some current interactive educational methods with various forms of training technologies is conditionally presented in Table 8 below.

The ease of use of some interactive learning methods in this table with various forms of educational technologies is somewhat conditional, and in fact, many other interactive methods can be used with specific educational technologies for specific purposes. It is necessary to emphasize that it is possible to apply.

One of the most serious didactic problems is the question of what depends on the choice of educational methods

In the didactics literature, it is noted that the correct selection of educational methods and the effectiveness of their application are related to various factors as follows:

- first of all, it depends on the didactic goals and tasks of training sessions
- Secondly, it depends on the nature of the material to be described;
- thirdly, it depends on the level of education and development of students;
- fourthly, it depends on the methods of the fundamentals of science studied in the educational process in a certain (current) period;
- fifthly, it depends on the conditions of the higher educational institution or the department;
- sixth, related to the material and technical support of the educational process;
- seventhly, it depends on the teacher's pedagogical skills, his preparation and level of organization of the educational process, and the teacher's knowledge of modern methods.

Thus, the process of professional education in higher education institutions is carried out within the framework of a multifaceted integrated system organized in accordance with modern forms and methods of education. In this case, each form fulfills its tasks, but the set of forms and methods forms a single didactic complex. The implementation of this didactic complex is determined by the psychological and pedagogical laws of the educational process.

Pedagogical technology has a subjective nature, that is, every pedagogue should creatively organize the education and upbringing process based on his ability and professional skills. regardless of pedagogical technologies:

- increase the effectiveness of pedagogical activity;
- establishing mutual cooperation between teachers and students;
- ensure that students acquire thorough knowledge of educational subjects;
- formation of independent, free and creative thinking skills in students;
- creating the necessary conditions for students to realize their potential;

The method of "brainstorming" ensures students' activity in the training process, encourages them to think freely, and frees them from the inertia of the same thinking - collecting diverse ideas on a specific topic, as well as solving creative tasks. serves to teach to overcome the thoughts that appeared at the initial stage of the process.

The mother tongue and reading literacy, mathematics, education, and natural sciences classes held in primary grades have a special place in the education system according to their essence, goals and tasks. After all, the foundations of literacy and moral-educational education are based on them. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to increasing students' interest in primary education classes. Because children should not get tired of the sacred word "lesson" from the elementary school. Today, experienced teachers use various didactic games to increase students' interest in lessons. Interactive method - by increasing the activity between the teacher and students in the educational process, they guarantee the assimilation of knowledge under the influence of their interaction, and serve to develop personal qualities. The use of these methods improves the quality and efficiency of the lesson. helps to increase. Its main criteria are holding informal debates, free presentation of educational material, independent reading, learning, conducting seminars, creating opportunities for students to take initiative, small group, large group, It consists of assignments, assignments, written works, etc. for working as a class team.

- Interactivity is the activity of two people, that is, the learning process takes place in the form of dialogue (computer communication) or on the basis of teacher-student interactions.

- Interactivity - mutual activity, movement, affectivity, occurs in student-teacher, student-student conversations.

The main goal of interactive methods is to create an environment for the active, free, creative thinking of the student, to use his needs, interests, internal capabilities by creating the most favorable environment and situation for the educational process. Such classes are conducted in such a way that no student is left out in this process, and they have the opportunity to clearly express their opinions that they have heard, read, and seen. A process of mutual exchange of ideas is created. Children's enthusiasm and interest in learning increases, mutual friendly relations are formed.

According to its nature, interactive education is based on didactic games, heuristic (thinking, searching, finding), creating and solving a problem situation by designing a conversation-lesson process, using information and communication technologies based on creativity. Education on the basis of information and communication technologies, in turn, consists of teaching with the help of computer programs, distance teaching, teaching on the basis of Internet networks, media-education methods.

In primary education, methods based on the design of heuristic conversations through didactic games according to the age characteristics, literacy levels, and personal nature of students are widely used. If in the process of teaching, every student worked on assignments at the level of his/her ability to learn, he/she would have ensured high quality and efficiency. Such a situation can be realized only through differentiated education. Now let's think about the implementation of educational processes through didactic games: Interactive game methods are based on the activation and acceleration of student activity. They are of great importance in identifying and implementing practical solutions for the realization and development of the student's creative potential.

The main types of interactive games are: intellectual (intelligent) and active and mixed games. These help students develop mental, physical, moral, spiritual, educational, psychological, aesthetic, artistic, entrepreneurship, creativity, work, and professional skills. leads to crying, free thinking, communication, creativity. In particular, it increases interest in learning about the environment, life, challenges, how to overcome obstacles, and develops critical thinking skills.

Observance of the following criteria in choosing interactive game types will give good results.

- games according to the composition of the participants, i.e. for boys, girls or mixed groups:
 - by the number of participants - single, pair, small group, large group, class team, inter-class and mass games:
 - thinking about the game process, thinking, gathering, based on actions, competition and others;
 - a lesson according to the time standard, a part of the training time allocated according to the plan, games that continue until the goal of the game is reached and the winners are determined.

All of this helps students to fully understand the scientific foundations of the structure of the universe by teaching them the interdisciplinary connection, and to form their scientific worldviews and develop their creative thinking. has a special place in the educational system.

After all, the foundations of literacy and moral-educational education are based on it. Therefore, the education of other subjects cannot be imagined without the education of reading. The student is faced with the ability to read the text correctly, quickly, understand it, and master its content for the first time in the reading classes. is entered.

Through native language and reading literacy classes, the way is opened for students to acquire educational skills and knowledge that are expected to be mastered according to the requirements of the State Education Standard (DTS). It is in reading education that a person's aspirations to understand his own self and the world are stimulated.

"Mother language and reading literacy" textbooks include various topics such as mother nature, the world around us, the history and present image of our country, the lives of adults and children, hard work, independence and national-spiritual values, friendship and peace. artistic, moral-educational, scientific-popular works intended to provide comprehensive understanding of

If the native language and reading literacy classes are organized in the style of introducing students to syllables, words and sentences and reading them, telling stories based on pictures, after mastering the reading technique reading is carried out on selected artistic, scientific and popular texts on certain topics.

Specific topics included in the "Mother Language and Reading Literacy" lessons of the primary grade are determined by introducing students to the magical world of fiction, focusing on the correct formation of their worldviews based on the ideology of national independence. Accordingly, the main feature of the reading classes is to ensure students' literacy, and to educate them in the spirit of high moral values based on the national ideology. The didactic tasks set for the mother tongue and reading literacy classes are as follows:

1. Students have good reading qualities: formation of correct, fast, conscious, expressive reading.
2. To teach students to use books, to get the necessary knowledge from them, to instill love for books; to raise them from an ordinary reader to the level of a thoughtful, creative reader.
3. Expanding and enriching students' knowledge about the environment and forming their scientific outlook.
4. Educating students to be morally, aesthetically mature and in the spirit of love for work.
5. Cultivating students' connected speech and literary-aesthetic thinking.
6. Enriching students' imagination.
7. Formation of elementary literary ideas

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